

Table S1. The correspondence of the reclassification of the land use and cover changes

Raster value	Label	Reclassify
0	no data	No-data
10	cropland, rainfed	Cropland
11	herbaceous cover	Cropland
12	tree or shrub cover	Cropland
20	cropland, irrigated or post-flooding	Cropland
30	mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover <50%)	Mosaic area
40	mosaic natural vegetation (trees, shrub, herbaceous cover >50% / cropland <50%)	Mosaic area
50	tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	Forest
60	tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	Forest
61	tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	Forest
62	tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	Forest
70	tree cover, needle leaved, even green, closed to open (>15%)	Forest
71	tree cover, needle leaved, even green, closed (>40%)	Forest
72	tree cover, needle leaved, even green, open (15-40%)	Forest
80	tree cover, needle leaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	Forest
81	tree cover, needle leaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	Forest
82	tree cover, needle leaved, deciduous, open (15-40%)	Forest
90	tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needle leaved)	Forest
100	mosaic tree and shrub (>50%)/ herbaceous cover (<50%)	Mosaic area
110	mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%)/ tree and shrub (<50%)	Mosaic area
120	shrubland	Forest
121	evergreen shrubland	Forest
122	deciduous shrub land	Forest
130	grassland	Grassland
140	lichens and mosses	Bare area
150	sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)	Forest
152	sparse shrub (<15%)	Forest
153	sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)	Forest
160	tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water	Forest
170	tree cover, flooded, saline water	Forest
180	shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh / saline / brackish water	Forest
190	urban areas	Built-up area
200	bare areas	Bare area
201	consolidated bare areas	Bare area
202	unconsolidated bare areas	Bare area
210	water bodies	Water area
220	permanent snow and ice	Water area

Table S2. The land use area of the loess plateau (km²) and the ratio (%) transition matrix in 1992-1997

Land use types	Cropland		Forest		Grassland		Mosaic area		Bare area		Built-up area		Water area		Total area
	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	
Cropland	162862.56	99.89	29.57	0.02	64.08	0.04	2.73	0.00	5.56	0.00	77.18	0.05	3.36	0.00	163045.03
Forest	221.90	0.30	72547.47	99.38	89.87	0.12	135.91	0.19	1.78	0.00	1.68	0.00	3.57	0.00	73002.18
Grassland	383.30	0.15	38.17	0.01	255350.44	99.68	217.50	0.08	33.14	0.01	131.61	0.05	5.14	0.00	256159.30
Mosaic area	172.72	0.13	637.50	0.47	61.14	0.04	135650.91	99.33	0.21	0.00	33.56	0.02	13.74	0.01	136569.78
Bare area	0.94	0.01	5.77	0.03	262.91	1.55	6.40	0.04	16655.38	98.34	4.82	0.03	0.00	0.00	16936.22
Built-up area	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1823.26	100.00	0.00	0.00	1823.26
Water area	4.93	0.28	0.31	0.02	10.07	0.58	4.40	0.25	0.00	0.00	1.26	0.07	1714.20	98.79	1735.17
Total	163646.35		73258.80		255838.50		136017.85		16696.07		2073.38		1739.99		649270.94

Table S3. The land use area of the loess plateau (km²) and the ratio (%) transition matrix in 1997-2003

Land use types	Cropland		Forest		Grassland		Mosaic area		Bare area		Built-up area		Water area		Total area
	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	
Cropland	162454.83	99.27	78.23	0.05	172.72	0.11	12.27	0.01	0.73	0.00	847.14	0.52	80.43	0.05	163646.35
Forest	255.04	0.35	71008.61	96.93	1786.24	2.44	183.42	0.25	16.15	0.02	7.55	0.01	1.78	0.00	73258.80
Grassland	1103.33	0.43	162.23	0.06	253032.20	98.90	674.84	0.26	87.46	0.03	758.73	0.30	19.72	0.01	255838.50
Mosaic area	82.01	0.06	2678.26	1.97	4948.79	3.64	128055.32	94.15	7.97	0.01	215.61	0.16	29.89	0.02	136017.85
Bare area	38.38	0.23	21.50	0.13	4152.20	24.87	63.13	0.38	12384.46	74.18	36.18	0.22	0.21	0.00	16696.07
Built-up area	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2073.38	100.00	0.00	0.00	2073.38
Water area	5.66	0.33	11.12	0.64	13.32	0.77	3.04	0.17	0.10	0.01	1.99	0.11	1704.76	97.97	1739.99
Total	163939.25		73959.96		264105.47		128992.01		12496.88		3940.58		1836.79		649270.94

Table S4. The land use area of the loess plateau (km²) and the ratio (%) transition matrix in 2003-2009

Land use types	Cropland		Forest		Grassland		Mosaic area		Bare area		Built-up area		Water area		Total area
	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	
Cropland	162103.20	98.88	27.58	0.02	102.98	0.06	3.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	1679.07	1.02	23.39	0.01	163939.25
Forest	166.01	0.22	73593.23	99.50	122.80	0.17	64.08	0.09	1.15	0.00	8.91	0.01	3.78	0.01	73959.96
Grassland	541.65	0.21	41.53	0.02	262215.30	99.28	265.53	0.10	13.74	0.01	1017.23	0.39	10.49	0.00	264105.47
Mosaic area	108.85	0.08	931.98	0.72	2854.65	2.21	124591.59	96.59	0.21	0.00	502.12	0.39	2.62	0.00	128992.01
Bare area	28.31	0.23	93.33	0.75	1168.56	9.35	15.42	0.12	11157.28	89.28	32.40	0.26	1.57	0.01	12496.88
Built-up area	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3940.58	100.00	0.00	0.00	3940.58
Water area	1.36	0.07	1.26	0.07	1.47	0.08	1.68	0.09	0.00	0.00	4.51	0.25	1826.51	99.44	1836.79
Total	162949.39		74688.90		266465.77		124941.33		11172.38		7184.82		1868.36		649270.94

Table S5. The land use area of the loess plateau (km²) and the ratio (%) transition matrix in 2009-2015

Land use types	Cropland		Forest		Grassland		Mosaic area		Bare area		Built-up area		Water area		Total area
	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	Area	Ratio	
Cropland	161107.78	98.87	24.96	0.02	207.54	0.13	1.36	0.00	0.73	0.00	1574.83	0.97	32.19	0.02	162949.39
Forest	47.61	0.06	74439.21	99.67	86.73	0.12	105.60	0.14	0.31	0.00	5.14	0.01	4.30	0.01	74688.90
Grassland	130.98	0.05	27.27	0.01	265221.49	99.53	283.46	0.11	21.29	0.01	757.16	0.28	24.12	0.01	266465.77
Mosaic area	7.45	0.01	165.59	0.13	987.66	0.79	123459.31	98.81	0.52	0.00	317.75	0.25	3.04	0.00	124941.33
Bare area	39.33	0.35	59.78	0.54	733.35	6.56	0.21	0.00	10327.34	92.44	8.70	0.08	3.67	0.03	11172.38
Built-up area	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	7184.82	100.00	0.00	0.00	7184.82
Water area	0.94	0.05	1.89	0.10	0.73	0.04	0.84	0.04	0.00	0.00	3.15	0.17	1860.80	99.60	1868.36
Total	161334.09		74718.69		267237.51		123850.79		10350.20		9851.55		1928.13		649270.94